

Studies on synthesis and antibacterial activity of some new Schiff bases, 4-thiazolidinones and 2-azetidinones

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Iodovanillin on condensation with different substituted aromatic amines yield Schiff bases (1a-e) which on cyclization with mercaptoacetic acid afford the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (2a-e). Compounds 1a-e on reaction with chloroacetyl chloride and Et₃N in dioxane furnish the respective 2-azetidinones (3a-e). All the compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against several bacteria.

Schiff bases possess antitubercular and anticancer activities¹. Various 4-thiazolidinones also possess wide range of pharmaceutical activities². A large number of 2-

on cyclization with mercaptoacetic acid afforded the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (2a-e). Reaction of chloroacetyl chloride and a mixture of 1a-e and Et₃N in dioxane afforded 2-azetidinones (3a-e) (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity was determined using disc diffusion method⁶ against *Escherichia coli* (Ec), *Azotobacter* (Az), *Bacillus subtilis* (Bs), *Salmonella typhi* (St) and *Salmonella dysentrea* (Sd). The compounds were tested at 150 ppm concentration using tetracycline as a standard for comparison. Compounds 1d, 2d, 2e and 3b were found to be moderately active against the above microbes and rest of the compounds feebly active than tetracycline.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-5-iodobenzylidene-(4-nitro)aniline (1a-e): To a mixture of iodovanillin (0.001 mol) and *p*-nitroaniline (0.001 mol) dissolved in ethanol (25 ml), one drop of acetic acid was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. It was then cooled and poured in cold water, and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol: 1a (60%), m.p. 130°; ν_{\max} 1672 (C=N) and 1595 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 4.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.1-7.6 (6H, m, ArH) and 8.5 (1H, s, CH=). Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 58-76%): 1b, m.p. 157°; c, 128°; d, 101°; e, 110°.

2-[3-Methoxy-4-hydroxy-5-iodophenyl]-3-[4'-nitrophenyl]-4-thiazolidinones (2a-e): To a mixture of compound 1 (0.001 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.001 mol) dissolved in dioxane (20 ml), a pinch of anhydrous zinc chloride was added and the mixture was refluxed for 8 h.

Scheme 1

azetidinones contain the β -lactam moiety³. Its reactivity is greatly influenced by different substituents⁴. 2-Azetidinones and its derivatives possess different therapeutic activities⁵. Herein we report the synthesis of several new Schiff bases, 4-thiazolidinones and 2-azetidinones with their antibacterial activity.

Iodovanillin was condensed with different substituted aromatic amines yielding Schiff bases 1a-e. Compound 1

On cooling, the separated solid was washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from ethanol to give **2** (yields 65–75%); ν_{\max} 1670 (C=O) and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=C), δ 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.15 (2H, s, CH_2S), 6.85 (1H, s, N-CH), 7.2–8.5 (6H, m, ArH) and 9.85 (1H, s, OH) : **2a**, m.p. 140°; **b**, 105°; **c**, 100°; **d**, 96°; **e**, 101°.

1-[4-Nitroaryl]-3-chloro-4-[3-iodo-4-hydroxy-5-methoxyaryl]-2-azetidinones (3a-e) : To a mixture of compound **1** (0.001 mol) and triethylamine (0.003 mol) dissolved in dioxane (25 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.0012 mol) was added dropwise at 10°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 6 h, then half of the solvent was removed by distillation and cooled. Separated solid was recrystallised from chloroform to give **3** (yields 61–73%); ν_{\max} 1764 (C=O) and 1609 cm^{-1} (C=C), δ 3.82 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.1 (1H, d, CH), 4.52 (1H, d, CHCl) and 7.3–8.25 (6H, m, ArH) : **3a**, m.p. 140°; **b**, 110°; **c**, 162°; **d**, 126°; **e**, 102°.

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

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